

Knowledge of Sharp Waste Management Among Health Care Workers in Selected Primary Health Care Centres in Ogun State

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Abstract

The study assessed the knowledge of health care workers on sharps waste management in selected primary health care centres in Ogun State. Cross-sectional survey design was adopted in the study. The study population was the health care workers in selected primary health care centres in two selected Local Government area of Abeokuta, Ogun State. The sample size of 182 was derived using Slovin's formula. Multistage sampling procedure was used in selecting the target samples. A well-structured questionnaire was designed to gathered information on the knowledge of the health care workers on the sharp waste management. The validity of the research instrument was done through face and content validity techniques. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages was used to answer the objective of the study. The results revealed that there was high level of knowledge of the healthcare workers on sharp waste management and waste categorization. It was recommended among others that Nursing Administrators should develop policies that will ensure total compliance to sharp waste management and waste categorization in the health care centres.

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Introduction

Hospital waste is a potential reservoir of pathogenic micro-organisms and requires appropriate, safe and reliable handling. The main risk associated with infection is sharps contaminated with blood. There should be a person or persons responsible for the organization and management of waste collection, handling, storage and disposal. Waste management should be conducted in coordination with the infection control team (Dilnasheen & Naseem, 2018).

Solid contaminated and non-contaminated waste should be disposed of separately. Solid contaminated waste should be placed in a plastic or galvanized metal container with a tightly fitting cover and housekeeping staff should wear personal protective equipment when handling contaminated waste. Waste containers for both contaminated and non-contaminated waste should be collected on a regular basis and the burnable ones transported to the incinerator or area for burning. Solid contaminated and non-contaminated waste should be disposed of separately. Solid contaminated waste should be placed in a plastic or galvanized metal container with a tightly fitting cover and housekeeping staff should wear personal protective equipment when handling contaminated waste (Garcia, 2019).

The main risk that is associated with infection comes from sharps contaminated with blood. Sharps include all objects and materials that pose a potential risk of injury and infection because of their puncture or cutting properties and these include syringes with needles, blades, wires, and broken glass. Syringes and needles should be disposed of immediately after use. The needle should not be recapped or removed from the syringe thus the whole combination should be inserted into the safety box directly after use. Sharps should be disposed of in safety boxes that are resistant to punctures and leakage and are designed so that items can be dropped in using one hand and no item can be removed. Sharps should not be handled unnecessarily to prevent needle prick injuries (Dilnasheen & Naseem, 2018).

Waste reduction, segregation and disposal are all crucial in sustaining a healthy environment and reducing subsequent public health implications and financial costs such as additional costs related to the disposal of wastes if not segregated appropriately (RCN, 2011). In the hospital setting, the problem of waste management is improper segregation of infectious and non-infectious wastes (Sarani, 2014). Hospital wastes must be segregated at their point of origin in order to prevent the occurrence of hospital acquired infections (Tirthankar, 2013).

The result from a study on waste generation and disposal in Bench Maji Zone of Ethiopia revealed that 57.9% of the total health centre waste produced in major health centres of this zone was general and the remaining 42.1% was hazardous health care waste. Of the total hazardous waste stream sharps, infectious and pathological wastes constitute highest with mean (\pm SD) 0.267 ± 0.107 (23.3%), 0.2695 ± 0.124 (23.6%), 0.441 ± 0.157 (38.6%) respectively in all health centres. The norm, according to the WHO guidelines, is that health centres produce 75% to 85% general healthcare waste, and 10% to 25% hazardous healthcare waste. This difference was attributed to large numbers of attendants in healthcare facilities during data collection, lack of appropriate health centre waste segregation practice according to WHO guideline and absence of any reusing or recycling activities (Meleko, Tesfaye & Henok, 2018).

Another study revealed that the respondents in the various facilities where the study was done had adequate knowledge of waste categorization. About 69.5% of the respondents rightly categorized paper, food, plastics and bottles as general waste. Soiled cotton wool, swab and gloves were also classified by 69.5% of the respondents as infectious wastes. The

majority of respondents also got it right by classifying body parts, body fluids and foetuses as pathological wastes. There was a significant association ($p < 0.05$) between the profession of the respondents and categorization of paper, bottles, food and plastic wastes. However, there were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between socio-demographic variables and categorization of soiled cotton wool, swab, specimen container, body parts, foetuses, needles and scalpels. The respondents in the various facilities had adequate knowledge of waste categorization. 61.0% indicated that segregation should be done at the source, as against 39.0% who indicated otherwise and 88.6 % indicated the use of safety boxes for sharp collection. About 81.9 % of the respondents also indicated the need to segregate medical wastes. The responses however differed from hospital to hospital as 85.7% of the respondents' agreed that medical waste could be generated from diagnosis, immunization, and treatment. About 74.3 % of the respondents also knew that there are specific procedures for collection and handling of medical waste by (Awodele, Adewoye, & Oparah, 2016). This study therefore, assessed the knowledge of health care workers on sharps waste management in selected primary health care centres in Ogun State.

Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. It involves the collection of baseline data that allows researchers to be relatively have confident on the instrument by self-administration of the questionnaire to the respondents where the variables of interest are not manipulate. The study population was the health care workers in selected primary health care centres in two selected Local Government area of Abeokuta, Ogun State. Health care workers included in the study were nurses, doctors, CHEWs and laboratory officers, at the selected Primary Health Care centres of two Local Government Area of Abeokuta, Ogun State, who have been working in the facilities for more than 6 months, willing to participate and available at the time of data collection. All the health care workers on their annual or maternity leave at time of data collection, all students who are under supervision and health care personnel who had worked in the selected PHC centres for less than six months were excluded.

To obtain the sample size for the study Slovin's formula (1960) was applied.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(R)^2}$$

The values used are

N= Study population (280),

R= 0.05 (margin of error)

n= sample size?

The computation for this is expressed below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(R)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{280}{1 + 280(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{280}{1 + 280(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{280}{1 + 0.7}$$

$$n = \frac{280}{1.7}$$

n= 164.7 (approximately 165)

165+ 10% (due to inappropriate filling of questionnaires) = 182

Therefore, the sample size for this study is **182**. Multistage sampling procedure was used in selecting the target samples. A well-structured questionnaire was designed to gathered information on the knowledge of the health care workers on the sharp waste management. The validity of the research instrument was done through face and content validity techniques. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages was used to answer the objective of the study

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Level of knowledge of sharp waste management

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
How should healthcare waste be disposed?	Dump directly into garbage bins	26	14.3
	Handing it over to health care waste management agency	61	33.5
	Sort according to type before disposing	92	50.5
	I don't know	3	1.6
	Total	182	100.0
Sharps are to be disposed only in designated container sharps waste?	Yes	151	83.0
	No	29	15.9
	I don't know	2	1.1
	Total	182	100.0
Used sharps and needles are disposed of in?	Yellow bags	11	6.0
	Puncture proof container	143	78.6
	Red bags	9	4.9
	I don't know	19	10.4
	Total	182	100.0
What should be the correct sequence sharps waste disposal.	Segregation < collection and storage < transport < treatment and disposal	122	67.0
	Collection < transport < disposal	44	24.2
	I don't know	16	8.8
	Total	182	100.0

Table 1 presents the level of knowledge of the healthcare workers on the sharp waste management. 92 (50.5%) of them do sort to type before disposing while (1.6%) did not know how the sharp waste should be disposed. Majority of the respondents 151 (83.0%) of the respondents said different containers are used to dispose sharps waste. 122 (67.0%) of the respondents believed that the correct sequence of sharps waste disposal is segregation < collection and storage < transport < treatment and disposal, 44 (24.2%) believed that the correct sequence of sharps waste disposal is collection < transport < disposal, 16 (8.8%) did not know the correct sequence.

This study revealed that there is high level of knowledge of the healthcare workers on the sharp waste management (50.5%) and waste categorization (83%). This is similar to the study by Awodele et al. (2016) that revealed that the 69.5% of respondents in the various facilities had adequate knowledge of waste categorization in a study conducted to assess the medical waste management in seven hospitals in Lagos state, Nigeria. A total of 67.0% of the respondents in this study segregate waste at the source of generation and sort according to type before disposing. This has been shown to be the key to achieving a sound sharp waste management as supported by the findings of Asadullah et al. (2015) in a study conducted in to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices regarding biomedical waste management among nursing staff in private hospitals in Udupi city, Karnataka, India.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that there is high level of knowledge of the healthcare workers on sharp waste management and waste categorization. **Continuing education efforts aimed at improving** sharp waste management and waste categorization **should be accorded high priority. Hence**, nursing educators should ensure that teachings on sharp waste management and waste categorization should be done in order to improve the knowledge and practices. Also, Nursing Administrators should develop policies that will ensure total compliance to sharp waste management and waste categorization in the health care centres.

References

- Asadullah, M.D., Karthik, G.K., & Dharmappa, B. (2013). A study on knowledge, attitude and practices regarding biomedical waste management among nursing staff in private hospitals in Udupi City, Karnataka, India. *Int J Geol Earth Environ Sci.* 3(1), 118–123
- Awodele, O., Adewoye, A.A., & Oparah, A.C. (2016). Assessment of medical waste management in seven hospitals in Lagos, Nigeria. *BMC Public Health*, 16(269). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-2916-1>.
- Dilnasheen, A., & Naseem R. (2018). The Knowledge of Standard Precautions among Nurses in Public and Private Tertiary Care hospital Labore. *National Journal of Health sciences*, 3, 76-82.
- Garcia S. (2019). High-level disinfection and sterilization: nurses should have a reprocessing knowledge, training and competency. *American Nurse today* 14(7). Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Meleko, A., Tesfaye, T., & Henok, A. (2018). Assessment of Healthcare Waste Generation Rate And Its Management System in Health Centres of Bench Maji Zone. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Sciences*, 28(2), 125-134. <https://doi:10.4314/ejhs.v28i2.4>.
- Sarani, H. (2014). Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Nurses about Standard Precaution for Hospital Acquired Infection in Teaching Hospitals Affiliated to Zabol University of Medical Science. *Global Journal of health science*, 4(2), 60 – 71
- Tirthankar, G. (2013). Occupational Health and Hazards among Health Care Workers. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Health*, 3(1), 1 – 4.

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